

CIRCULATORY MEASUREMENTS DATA PROCESSING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

A new system for shipboard processing of circulatory survey data has been implemented by the National Ocean Survey (NOS). Hardware requirements, software design, and preliminary results of certification testing and field use are presented with sample outputs.

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1. Introduction

A common problem in oceanographic data collection is the loss of observations at an important site because of mechanical malfunction of instrumentation. The problem is often not discovered until data reduction begins at a later time.

Prior to 1981, the NOS was largely dependent on a processing system at the Rockville Headquarters to determine the quality of data taken at a particular station. After preliminary processing, if an important data set was determined to be unacceptable for analysis and subsequent publication in the NOS products, the decision to redeploy a new set of instruments to retake the data was delayed at least a week, often more, after initial recovery of instrumentation.

With the acquisition of PDP-11/34 minicomputers for the survey vessels, NOAA Ships FERREL and McARTHUR, and the development of easy to use software, the question of whether or not to redeploy instrumentation can be decided while the ship is still on site. All meteorological, CTD, and current meter data can be processed through the preliminary stages with a single set of software, using one procedure and one translator, consolidating both hardware and software requirements for many data types.

2. Software Capabilities and Hardware Requirements

The new system is called Circulatory Measurements Data Processing (CMDP). In its present form,

CMDP allows an oceanographic vessel to perform a preliminary reduction of the data to the point where the commanding officer has the necessary information at hand for a complete on site evaluation of the quality of the data which has have been recovered. The system can display raw data, plot it graphically, convert it to engineering units, and perform automated time checking, all within an hour or so of recovery. Instrument malfunction statistics are also collected and made available in graphic form to the shipboard electronics personnel for more rapid diagnosis of those instruments in need of maintenance or repair.

The computer hardware on both ships is identical (Figure 1). It consists of a PDP-11/34 minicomputer with 128K bytes of memory, two RX02 floppy disc drives for program and information storage, two TS03 tape drives, a Gould 5005 printer/plotter, and a VT100 CRT for operator inputs.

Hardware Requirements for CMDP System
Figure 1

The system can process data from Aanderaa current meters, meteorological packages, water level recorders, Grundy current meters, and Applied Microsystems, Ltd., (AML) CTD units.

The instrument tape is transcribed with a Telex 1024 tape drive, through an amplifier into a CAMAC data handling crate. The signal is converted from analog to digital by a converter board designed by Aanderaa. After it is converted, the data are stored in computer memory until the operator has completed processing. Then it is written out to two computer-compatible tapes, one for transmittal and one for archival to insure data preservation.

3. Software Design

The software allows extreme flexibility; it is composed of subroutine modules called states, each of which performs its function independently. Therefore, if the software requires modification or extension of its function, a new or existing module can be developed and inserted into the system with a minimum effect on the other states.

The CMDP system consists of three separate programs. Program TABGEN creates a series of tables containing such survey information as exact station position, mooring configuration and necessary timing and calibration data. These entries are automatically retrieved for use at various stages in the processing.

Program WRTDY is used to initialize the computer tapes used by CMDP by writing preliminary data describing blocking size, etc. Program CMDP is the primary data handling routine used to transfer and process the data in computer memory. It steps through sequenced stages of processing called states, retrieving necessary information contained in the station and calibration files. Figure 2 illustrates the flow through the modular states and the interaction between the peripheral devices and the system.

Data Flow Through CMDP
Figure 2

The preliminary states through state 32 perform an initial hardware checkout of the system and peripheral devices. The data stream read into the system is identified and tables are checked to insure all data necessary to complete processing are on the floppy discs. In state 36, the raw data are read in, either directly from the instrument tape, or as a partially processed record from the nine-track drives. This allows the operator some flexibility in deciding how much time he wishes to spend on a particular record. He can output a troublesome record to tape and return to complete the processing later. During processing, TABGEN builds information tables which keep statistics on suspected instrument malfunctions, tape transcription problems, and a complete history of the processing changes made for every instrument tape. This information is written onto the output tape and transmitted to Rockville with its associated data stream for final processing and analysis.

Once in computer memory, data are assessed for errors in individual word or record lengths. Data words that are more or less than ten-bits are graphically displayed as an "error flag" histogram to locate their relative position in the data stream. The location of long and short records (usually more than or less than 6 words) are graphically displayed in a "sync flag" histogram (Figure 3).

Histogram Display of Errors Compiled During
Transcription
Figure 3

After state 40, the raw instrument numbers can be either displayed on the CRT or printed. Following alignment of the data record using the synchronization pulse, manual alignment and limited editing are performed in state 48.

Time Series Plot From State 56
Figure 4

("Alignment" is the process of correcting for missing or extra words.) After this alignment is completed, graphic time series plots (Figure 4) are available to the operator.

A conversion from instrument numbers to engineering units using the calibration tables can be requested in state 56. To complete processing, a preliminary time check of the record is done which compares the expected number of records, computed from elapsed time and sampling rate, and the number of points actually observed. These checks can be performed between events visible in the data stream (e.g., meter turned, meter into water, meter out of water, meter turned off, etc.), the times of which have been carefully logged.

Depending on which processing states are successfully completed, three different output formats are available: an OD record, which is raw and unaligned, a 2D record which has been successfully aligned and edited, or a 4D record which has been aligned and time checked.

4. Outputs and Applications of the System

One of the two output tapes is then sent to Rockville where separate software translates it to a form compatible with the NOS UNIVAC mainframe and integrates it into NOS in-house processing and analysis software. If all states are successfully completed, the output tape contains OD, 2D, and 4D versions of each data stream, an alignment changes file containing the complete history of changes made to the data during onboard processing, and a translator monitor file containing the translation and instrument malfunction information. The calibration and station data used for the entire survey are also copied as a separate table. As an additional check, the information used in processing a particular record is recorded in a heading block preceding each data stream. This simplifies the task of assembling the information required when more intensive data checking and analysis are done in Rockville. The information tables with each transmittal are further utilized for statistical studies of meter performance and to track drift of the calibration transfer function as the meter ages. Development of statistics for an entire survey is possible in a relatively short time for incorporation into NOS's Data Quality Assurance program.

5. Certification

To insure the quality of the data processed using the new system, a rigorous program of certification was undertaken. All instrument types to be processed by this system were processed in parallel with the old NOS processing system (using an Oregon State University translator), and the new CMDP system and the outputs were compared using specially written software. The results were compared both in engineering units and instrument numbers for 48 15-day records of data. A maximum percent of errors for any one file approached 1/2 percent infrequently, with

most files giving less than 1/4 percent bad comparisons. Errors were divided evenly between the two systems. Further investigation has indicated that these errors arise from the different way in which the two A - D translators attempt to rectify bad bit patterns found on the original instrument tapes, or from low level input signals, which caused some bits to be misread. This problem is being addressed now by NOS as part of a complete examination of the "front end" of data acquisition and processing.

6. Enhancements and Applications

Some prototype enhancements, beyond the original design, have been included in our current version of the software; others are being tested and planned for inclusion in future versions of the software. We are developing a two-pass editing system as the next major enhancement for CMDP. The first pass will employ logical algorithms to identify electronic or bit problems, while the second pass will be a statistical editing function. Most electronic or bit malfunctions of instrumentation have characteristics which an algorithm can be designed to identify and correct. We presently have two algorithms operating which compensate for the slow inertial response of the instruments to direction changes during slack water in rotary and reversing tidal currents. If an algorithm correction is made by the computer, the changed data point is flagged in the graphics output and the change is recorded in the AC file. We are evaluating different schemes for the statistical editing, taking into account the limitation of memory size and the relative efficiency of each approach.

Some basic forms of analysis are also planned for inclusion in the near future. We have completed the conversion of a harmonic analysis program to run on the PDP-11/34. Additions of some other forms of oceanographic analyses such as ellipse programs and additional graphics capabilities are also proposed.

7. Summary and Conclusions

The automated system developed by NOS has reduced the time spent in laborious manual time checking, transcription, and alignment. It has allowed NOS to utilize its limited resources more efficiently.

The larger and more expensive mainframe computer is utilized more for analysis, larger scale microfilm plotting and modeling programs, which require large memory size. CMDP has allowed our staff to devote more time to analysis of the processed records for inclusion in NOS's series of technical and data reports. The use of instrument statistics by ship's electronics personnel alerts them to problems identified during data translations, e.g., as bad bit patterns or short and long word counts. This timely precautionary maintenance minimizes the malfunction of instrumentation and the necessity of redeployment. The system's capability for quick response in the field was demonstrated

recently in New York Harbor. Twenty-four hours after a maritime accident, the NOAA Ship FERREL, deployed current meters near the site at the request of the Coast Guard. Within 1½ hours of recovering the instrumentation, processed data were available to the Coast Guard.

The first phase of a program for preliminary data reduction on board NOS circulatory survey vessels has been completed. CMDP has already significantly reduced the processing time and effort required to each data record. NOS is developing a phased-in series of enhancements to this software to extend its capabilities.